

THE IMPACT OF SERVANT LEADERSHIP ON ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT, WORK ENGAGEMENT AND EMPLOYEE WELL-BEING. THE MEDIATING ROLE OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY IN PAKISTAN'S EDUCATION SECTOR

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Abstract

In present global dynamics and complex organizational systems, the pursuit for sustainability has become vitally important. Leadership and Corporate Social Responsibility remain two of the most crucial components to organization's success. This research investigates the impact of Servant Leadership on Organizational Commitment, Employee Work Engagement and Employee Well-being among Pakistani education sector. This study also investigates the mediating effect of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). A random sample of 239 of employees from private universities was drawn to examine these relationships. These interactions among the variables were assessed through Structural Equation Modelling. The data analysis was performed by SmartPLS 4. The results indicate that Servant Leadership has a positive impact on Organizational Commitment, Employee Work Engagement and Employee Well-being. Moreover, Corporate Social Responsibility also further supports this link and mediates the relationship suggesting that organizations perceived as socially responsible enhance the positive effects of Servant Leadership in an organization. This study provides useful information to leaders and management of organizations to develop and adopt CSR policies that enhance employee commitment, engagement and well-being for sustainable future of organizations.

INTRODUCTION

In present dynamics of organizational landscape, the leadership styles play a fundamental role in shaping employee outcomes. These outcomes include organizational commitment, work engagement, and overall wellbeing of the employees. Among the numerous leadership

styles, servant leadership – which is characterized by a leader's commitment and devotion to serving the needs of employees and fostering their development rather than his/her personal interests, has gained considerable attention (Eva et al., 2019). Servant leadership which has core principles of empathy, stewardship, and

community building (Greenleaf, 1977), fosters and encourages a people-centered culture in the organization that not only enhances employees overall job satisfaction but also increases their attachment, engagement, loyalty, and dedication to the organization.

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) also has arisen as an essential practice of the organizations that reflects and indicates commitment to environmental and social concerns rather than just maximization of profits (Aguinis & Glavas, 2012). The initiatives of CSR can build a sense of meaningfulness at workplace among the workers, which results in strengthening their psychological affiliation with the organization (Glavas, 2016). Recent study (Sousa & van Dierendonck, 2017) in the domain of servant leadership style suggests that a leader who emphasizes service to employees and others influences the perception of employees of CSR. These perspectives result in employee-related outcomes such as commitment, humility, action and employee engagement.

Amidst growing interest in leadership styles and CSR, there is a need for comprehensive empirical research of how servant leadership is associated with employee related outcomes via the component of CSR. It is important to understand this mediational relationship in the times where stakeholders demand a leader with ethical considerations and who demonstrates social responsibility. Therefore, this research investigates the impact of servant leadership on employee related outcomes of organizational commitment, work engagement and employee wellbeing. It also focuses on the mediating role of CSR between these relationships.

Our study is supported by Social Exchange Theory (SET) by (Blau, 1964) which proposes that relationships are built on reciprocal exchanges: when employees feel supported and valued by their leaders and organizations, they reciprocate with positive attitudes and behaviours like commitment, engagement and wellbeing. In our study, servant leadership represents the organization giving to the employees in the shape of support, care and empowerment. CSR initiatives enhance employee's belief that organization acts ethically and responsibly. In

return, employees give back through organizational commitment, work engagement and experience wellbeing.

Problem Statement

Despite the positive impact of servant leadership on employee outcomes, and a growing global interest in the topic, there is a significant literature gap. Moreover, the practice of CSR is recognized as essential in reinforcing the leadership and stakeholder engagement, its mediating role between servant leadership and employee outcomes has not been studied sufficiently. Without a clear knowledge of these linkages, educational leaders may have a tough time implementing strategies that affect commitment to the organization, engagement at work, and employee wellbeing.

This study aims to address this gap by examining how servant leadership impacts employee outcomes with CSR as a mediator. This research aims to provide valuable empirical insights that can encourage better leadership practices and development of policies around it Pakistan's education sector.

Research Questions

1. What is the impact of Servant Leadership on corporate Social Responsibility?
2. What is the relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility and; Organizational Commitment, Work Engagement and Employee Wellbeing?
3. Does Corporate Social Responsibility mediate between Servant Leadership and; Organizational Commitment, Work Engagement, and Employee Wellbeing?

Research Objectives

- To study the relationship between Servant Leadership and Corporate Social Responsibility
- To examine the relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility and; Organizational Commitment, Work Engagement and Employee Wellbeing.

- To study the mediation effect Corporate Social Responsibility between Servant Leadership and; Organizational Commitment, Work Engagement, and Employee Wellbeing

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

Servant Leadership

Servant leadership, introduced by Greenleaf (1977), emphasizes the leader's role as a servant first. He/she prioritizes the needs of others and fosters the development of employees. Unlike traditional leadership styles that are focused on organizational goals and personal achievements, servant leaders aim to promote ethical behaviour, build community and empower employees (Eva et al., 2019). The literature in servant leadership has consistently demonstrated a positive employee outcome, including organizational citizenship behaviours, job satisfaction, and lower turnover intentions (Liden et al., 2014). By creating an environment that is supportive, servant leaders nurture trust, enhance intrinsic motivation which contributes to higher levels of employee satisfaction and performance (Eva et al., 2019). Servant Leadership inherently aligns with the principles of CSR, as both to stakeholder wellbeing, emphasize ethical behaviour and a commitment to the greater good beyond profits and financial performance (Liden et al., 2014). Leaders who adopt a style of servant leadership naturally promote CSR by prioritizing the needs of employees, communities, customers, and the environment. By support of the literature, we propose following hypothesis:

H1 – Servant Leadership is positively associated with Corporate Social Responsibility

Organizational Commitment

Organizational Commitment refers to the psychological attachment and affiliation an employee feels with their organization (Meyer & Allen, 1991). It comprises of affective, continuance, and normative dimensions, with affective commitment that shows emotional attachment being most desirable (Meyer et al., 2002). Servant leadership practices that reflect

recognition, fairness, and employee development have been studied to have a positive impact on organizational commitment (Sousa & van Dierendonck, 2017). Employees who perceive their leaders as genuinely empathetic and caring are more likely to reciprocate with engagement and loyalty. Leadership style has been identified as a critical antecedent of employee commitment; servant leadership with its increased emphasis on employee empowerment and development, has been found to increase the levels of emotional attachment and sense of belonging to the organization (Hunter et al., 2013). CSR activities can fulfill employees psychological needs for meaning and purpose at workplace, which in turn increases their affective commitment to the organization (De Roeck & Delobbe, 2012). Employees view CSR engagement as a reflection of shared values, leading them to invest more emotionally in the organization. Hence we propose the following hypothesis:

H2a – Corporate Social Responsibility positively affects Organizational Commitment

Work Engagement

Work engagement is defined as a positive, fulfilling, work-related state characterized by dedication, vigor and absorption (Schaufeli et al., 2002). Leadership behaviours are essential antecedents of work engagement; supportive leadership styles such as servant leadership enhance employees' psychological resources, increasing their involvement and motivation at work (Bakker & Demerouti, 2008). Servant leadership can increase intrinsic motivation in employees, by focusing on employees' personal growth in organization and wellbeing, resulting in boosting work engagement (van Dierendonck, 2011). Though authentic care and service, servant leaders help employees find a deeper meaning in their work, leading to an increased level of engagement. CSR activities fulfill employees' higher order psychological needs, such as purpose, belongingness, and self-esteem, which are key drivers of work engagement (Aguinis & Glavas, 2012). Employees perceive their work as more meaningful when it contributes to broader societal

goals, enhancing their vigor, dedication and absorption. We propose the following hypothesis:
H2b – Corporate Social Responsibility positively affects Work Engagement

Employee Wellbeing

Employee wellbeing encompasses psychological, physical and emotional aspects of employees’ health at work (Danna & Griffin, 1999). Servant Leadership promotes wellbeing by reducing job stressors, enhancing social support, and fostering a meaningful work environment (Eva et al., 2019). Research shows that leadership practices that align with employees’ values and need to contribute lower burnout rates and higher life satisfaction (Neubert et al., 2009). By emphasizing empathy, stewardship, and trust, servant leaders help to cultivate psychologically safe workplaces where employees thrive. Employees who perceive their organizations as socially responsible report a higher level of wellbeing, including greater job satisfaction, emotional resilience, and life satisfaction (Lee et al., 2013). CSR enhances employees’ sense of belonging and pride, contributing to their overall mental health. We propose following hypothesis:

H2c – Corporate Social Responsibility positively affects Employee Well-being

Corporate Social Responsibility

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has been a topic of interest over the decades and has continued to grow in impact and significance. It has influenced major research, commentary,

debate and theory building. It is also widely accepted by the businesses today that commit to the practices of CSR is key to the sustainability of businesses (Wood, 2002), Resulting the increase in humanitarian activities. CSR reflects an organization’s commitment to ethical practices, environmental stewardship, and community development (Carroll, 1991). Employees’ perceptions of CSR influence their identification with the organization. This results in fostering positive attitudes such as engagement, commitment and wellbeing (Glavas, 2016). Servant leaders though their ethical and altruistic behaviour, are most likely to cultivate a strong CSR orientation within the organizations (Liden et al., 2014). Servant leadership may influence employee’s perception of CSR, as leaders who prioritize stewardship and service that often fosters CSR initiatives (Lemoine et al., 2019). Studies have found that CSR mediates the relationship between leadership behaviours and employee outcomes (Farooq et al., 2017), suggesting that CSR acts as a crucial psychological mechanism that links servant leadership to employees’ positive work experiences. We propose the following hypotheses:

H3a – Corporate Social Responsibility mediates between Servant Leadership and Organizational Commitment

H3b – Corporate Social Responsibility mediates between Servant Leadership and Work Engagement

H3c – Corporate Social Responsibility mediates between Servant Leadership and Employee Well-being

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

METHODOLOGY

This research is conducted in the education sector of Pakistan. It aims to study how servant leadership affects organizational commitment, work engagement and wellbeing of the employees. Moreover, how corporate social responsibility acts as a mediating role in the relationship. The findings of this research will assist managers to create policies that encourage CSR initiatives that enhance organizational commitment, work engagement and employee wellbeing. The target population for this research is employees in higher education institute. The data was collected from employees at all levels and working in different departments such as administration, faculty, and supportive staff. This research adopts a cross-sectional survey mode to collect data. A self-administered questionnaire is used containing scale for variable measurement is presented to the respondents to collect data. SmartPLS 4 was used to analyze the model using Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). Mediation analysis was performed through bootstrapping technique,

Data Collection Instrument and Measurement Scales

For the present research, approximately 250 questionnaires were distributed among the respondents belonging to the educational sector through physically. A total number of 94 responses were received through Google forms. 183 were received through physical responses. The response rate was approximately 73.2% from physical questionnaires. A total of 266 responses were received from both physical and online medium. From 266 questionnaires 27 were omitted due to improper responses.

Servant Leadership

Servant leadership was measured with scale by Liden et al. (2015). Participants were asked to rate the presence of servant leadership in their institute on a scale of 5point Likert scale.

Corporate Social Responsibility

Corporate Social Responsibility was measured with scale by Turker. (2009). Participants were asked to rate the corporate social responsibility in their institute on a scale of 5point Likert scale.

Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment was measured with scale by Allen and Meyer. (2015). Participants were asked to rate the organizational commitment in their institute on a scale of 5point Likert scale.

Work Engagement

Work engagement was measured with scale by Schaufeli et al., (2002). Participants were asked to rate the work engagement in their institute on a scale of 5point Likert scale.

Employee Wellbeing

Employee Wellbeing was measured with scale by Skevington et al. (2004). Participants were asked to rate employee wellbeing in their institute on a scale of 5point Likert scale.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This section discusses the results of the data analysis conducted to examine the impact of Servant Leadership on employee related outcomes in Pakistan's education sector. Data was analyzed through SmartPLS 4. Demographic analysis, reliability and validity tests, correlation analysis, and hypothesis testing conducted through Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) are discussed.

Sample characteristics

A total number of 239 responses were used for this study. To assess the demographics in the sample, 6 key variables were observed to summarize the distribution of gender, age group, experience, and education level. The demographics wise distribution of the sample is presented in Table 1 below.

Demographic profile of respondents

Variable	Categories	Frequency (N=239)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	135	56.5%
	Female	104	43.5%
Age Group	21-30 years	76	31.7%
	31-40 years	110	46.0%
	41-50 years	39	16.3%
	Above 50 years	14	5.8%
	Less than 5 years	64	26.7%
Experience	5-10 years	95	39.7%
	11-20 years	55	23.2%
	More than 20 years	25	10.4%
Education Level	Bachelor	72	30.1%
	Master	149	62.4%
	PhD	18	7.5%

Out of 239 respondents, majority of respondents were male (n = 135, 56.5 %) while (n = 104, 43.5 %) participants were female. Age was categorized into four groups, the largest age group was 31-40 years (n = 110, 46.0 %), followed by 21-30 years (n = 76, 31.7 %), 41-50 years (n = 39, 16.3 %), and finally the smallest group was above 50 years (n = 14, 5.8 %). Work experience was categorized into four groups. Majority of respondents had experience of 5-10 years (n = 95, 39.7%) followed by less than 5 years (n = 64, 26.7 %), 11-20 years (n = 55, 23.2 %) and finally the smallest group was more than 20 years of experience (n = 25, 10.4 %). The education level of respondents was also

measured with majority of respondents were at least Masters/Postgraduate degree holders (n = 149, 62.4 %) followed by Bachelors/Undergraduate degree holders (n = 72, 30.1 %) and finally Doctorate/Ph.D. (n=18, 7.5%).

Reliability and validity analysis

The reliability and validity of instruments is essential for any research. Here we measure the Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for the constructs. The values of the reliability and validity analysis are given below in Table 2 below.

Table 2
Reliability and validity of constructs

Construct	Items	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability (CR)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Servant Leadership (SL)	7	0.75	0.77	0.72
Organizational Commitment (OC)	8	0.81	0.82	0.68
Work Engagement (WE)	17	0.76	0.79	0.71
Employee Wellbeing (EW)	9	0.74	0.70	0.63
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	5	0.71	0.75	0.67

Cronbach's Alpha values for Servant leadership are 0.75, composite reliability is calculated as 0.77

and the values for Average Variance Extracted (AVE) are 0.72, confirming the validity and

reliability of seven items used to assess this construct. For the mediator CSR, Cronbach's Alpha values are 0.71, composite reliability is calculated as 0.75 and the values for Average Variance Extracted (AVE) are 0.67, confirming the validity and reliability of five items used. The Cronbach's Alpha value for variable of Organizational Commitment is 0.81, the composite reliability is calculated as 0.82 and AVE is 0.68, confirming the dependability and stability of this variable for its 8-items scale. Cronbach Alpha of the variable of Work Engagement is 0.76,

the composite reliability is calculated as 0.79 and AVE is 0.71. Cronbach Alpha of the variable of Employee Wellbeing is 0.74, the composite reliability is calculated as 0.70 and AVE is 0.63 confirming the reliability and validity of nine-item scale. Discriminant validity explains the extent to which variables are different from each other. One of the most common methods of measuring discriminant validity is Fornell and Larcker (1981) criterion. The values for Fornell Larcker Criterion are given in the table below

Table 3
Fornell Larker Criterion

	SL	OC	WE	EW	CSR
SL	0.825				
OC	0.642	0.815			
WE	0.701	0.651	0.802		
EW	0.613	0.672	0.603	0.823	
CSR	0.712	0.726	0.682	0.707	0.842

Correlation

The correlation analysis studies the interrelationships between the constructs in the study. They provide valuable insights regarding their associations. It measures the strength of the relationship and the direction of a linear relationship between two quantitative constructs. A correlation coefficient of 0.00 to 0.29 less is

considered very weak, between 0.3 to 0.49 is considered low correlation, between 0.5 to 0.69 is considered moderate correlation, between 0.7 to 0.89 is considered high correlation and correlation coefficient between 0.9 to 1 is considered very high and strong (A.G. Asuero, 2006). The values of correlations of the studied variables are presented in the table below:

Table 4
Correlations Analysis

	SL	OC	WE	EW	CSR
SL	1				
OC	0.594**	1			
WE	0.656**	0.686**	1		
EW	0.726**	0.695**	0.621**	1	
CSR	0.711**	0.742**	0.644**	0.671**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The results of the correlation matrix explain that Servant Leadership is significantly and positively correlated with Organizational Commitment (r = 0.594, p < 0.01), strong positively correlated with Work Engagement (r = 0.656, p < 0.01), positively

correlated with Employee Wellbeing (r = 0.726, p < 0.01) and significantly correlated with Corporate Social Responsibility (r = 0.711, p < 0.01). Organizational Commitment is also significantly and positively correlated to Work Engagement (r = 0.686, p < 0.01), positively correlated to Employee Wellbeing (r = 0.695, p < 0.01) and

similarly positively correlated with Corporate Social Responsibility ($r = 0.698, p < 0.01$). Work Engagement is also significantly and positively correlated to Employee Wellbeing ($r = 0.621, p < 0.01$) and positively correlated to Corporate Social Responsibility ($r = 0.644, p < 0.01$). Lastly, Employee Wellbeing is found to be significantly and positively correlated with Corporate Social Responsibility ($r = 0.671, p < 0.01$).

Hypotheses Testing

The hypotheses among the variables were studied with path coefficients and values were analyzed using Bootstrapping technique using Smart PLS 4. Path coefficients, t values and p values help us analyze the conditions for acceptance and rejection of proposed hypotheses in this research.

Table 5
Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis	Path Coefficient	t value	p value	Result
SL→CSR	0.476	4.512	0.00	Accepted
CSR→OC	0.673	6.891	0.00	Accepted
CSR→WE	0.712	6.441	0.00	Accepted
CSR→EW	0.687	7.652	0.00	Accepted

The results from bootstrapping affirm that there is a strong positive significant relationship between Servant Leadership and Corporate Social Responsibility with (path coefficient = 0.476, t statistics = 4.512 and p value = 0.000). Thus, our proposed hypothesis 1 is supported that Servant Leadership positively influences Corporate Social Responsibility. The relationship between Corporate Social Responsibility, Organizational Commitment (path coefficient = 0.673, t statistics = 6.891 and p-value = 0.000); Corporate Social

Responsibility, Work Engagement (path coefficient = 0.712, t statistics = 6.441 and p-value = 0.000), and Corporate Social Responsibility, Organizational Employee Wellbeing (path coefficient = 0.687, t statistics = 7.652 and p-value = 0.000) are also found significant. Therefore, our proposed hypotheses 2a, 2b and 2c are supported by this analysis that Corporate Social Responsibility positively influences Organizational Commitment, Work Engagement and Employee Wellbeing.

Table 6
Mediation Analysis

Hypothesis	Path Coefficient	t value	p value	Result
SL→CSR→OC	0.261	4.810	0.00	Accepted
SL→CSR→WE	0.313	6.341	0.00	Accepted
SL→CSR→EW	0.267	5.611	0.00	Accepted

The mediation analysis was performed using bootstrapping technique to assess the mediating role of Corporate Social Responsibility in the relationship between Servant Leadership and Organizational Commitment (path coefficient = 0.261, t = 4.810, p = 0.00), Work Engagement (path coefficient = 0.313, t = 6.341, p = 0.00), and Employee Wellbeing (path coefficient = 0.267, t = 5.611, p = 0.00). The results indicate a significant mediating effect of Corporate Social

Responsibility on Servant Leadership and Organizational Commitment, Work Engagement and Employee Wellbeing. Therefore, the proposed hypotheses 3a, 3b and 3c for mediation are supported by this result.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This study examined the pivotal role of servant leadership in shaping organizational commitment, work engagement, and employee wellbeing, with

corporate social responsibility (CSR) serving as a key mediating mechanism. Grounded in Social Exchange Theory, the findings underscore that servant leaders not only foster a supportive and ethical work environment but also cultivate strong CSR perceptions among employees. These perceptions, in turn, enhance employees' emotional attachment to the organization, drive their engagement at work, and promote their overall psychological wellbeing. By integrating leadership behavior with socially responsible organizational practices, this research highlights the interconnectedness of leadership, CSR, and critical employee outcomes. Practically, the study suggests that organizations aiming to boost employee commitment, engagement, and wellbeing should invest in developing servant leadership behaviors and authentic CSR initiatives. Theoretically, the findings contribute to the growing body of literature linking leadership styles with CSR and employee-centered outcomes, offering valuable insights for future research. Overall, this study reinforces the idea that socially responsible leadership not only benefits external stakeholders but is also vital for fostering a healthy, engaged, and committed workforce internally, ultimately driving sustainable organizational success.

Theoretical contributions and Practical Implications

This study offers several important theoretical contributions to the fields of leadership, corporate social responsibility (CSR), and organizational behavior. By applying Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964), this research deepens the understanding of how servant leadership behaviors initiate reciprocal positive outcomes, mediated through CSR perceptions. It highlights CSR as a key relational mechanism linking leadership and employee outcomes. The study bridges two traditionally separate streams of research—servant leadership and CSR—by demonstrating that leadership style not only influences internal organizational dynamics but also shapes employees' perceptions of broader social responsibilities. This study advances theoretical knowledge by positioning CSR perceptions as a mediator, rather than a direct

predictor, of organizational commitment, work engagement, and wellbeing, offering a nuanced understanding of how and why leadership impacts employees. By simultaneously examining organizational commitment, work engagement, and wellbeing, the study provides a more holistic view of employee responses to socially responsible leadership, contributing to a more integrated model of positive organizational behavior.

Limitations and Future Research Directions

While this study offers important insights into the relationship between servant leadership, corporate social responsibility (CSR), and employee outcomes, it is not without limitations, which suggest opportunities for future research. Firstly, the study's cross-sectional design limits the ability to infer causality among the variables. Although theoretical frameworks such as Social Exchange Theory provide a strong basis for the proposed relationships, longitudinal or experimental studies are needed to establish causal links more definitively. Secondly, the research relies on self-reported data, which raises the possibility of common method bias. Although procedural remedies may have been employed, future research should incorporate multi-source data, such as supervisor ratings or objective CSR metrics, to enhance validity. Thirdly, the study may be limited by cultural context if conducted within a specific region or industry. Cultural values influence perceptions of leadership and CSR; thus, future studies could examine whether these relationships hold across different cultural settings and organizational types. Fourthly, this study focuses on CSR perceptions as a single mediating variable. Future research could explore additional mediators (e.g., organizational identification, perceived organizational support) or moderators (e.g., individual values, ethical climate) that may further explain the complex relationships between servant leadership and employee outcomes. Finally, while this study centers on servant leadership, future studies could compare the effects of different leadership styles (e.g., transformational, ethical, authentic leadership) on CSR perceptions and employee wellbeing to better

understand the unique and overlapping mechanisms at play.

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